

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

The effects of biofertilizers and inorganic fertilizers on soil microorganism abundance, microbial community structure, and functional gene diversity in broccoli crops.

Soil management significantly impacts agricultural ecosystem biodiversity, potentially leading to soil carbon depletion, biodiversity loss, and microbial community structure changes due to various practices. Plant Growth-Promoting Microorganisms (PGPM) exert direct and indirect effects on plant growth: phytohormone production, increasing the availability of nutrients and water, and protecting the plant from a variety of biotic and abiotic stresses. The use of PGPM in agriculture could help mitigate the negative impacts caused by massive inputs. The objectives of this study were to compare the use of PGPM with the reduction of inorganic fertilizers in a broccoli crop and to determine whether this management could modify the abundance of soil microorganisms, the soil microbial community structure, and the diversity of functional

genes related to C and N cycles. Four treatments were applied: a) F100 (conventional fertilization); b) BA+FU (PGPM + 50% of fertilization reduction); c) BA (PGPM + 50% of fertilization reduction); d) F50 (50% of fertilization reduction). Fertilization reduction did not affect broccoli production. Results showed that reduced fertilization with the addition of biofertilizers had no significant effect on soil nutrients, microbial abundance, structure, microbial activity, or yield compared to conventional inorganic fertilization. Microbial inoculants were ineffective in enhancing soil microbial abundance and activity. The problem might be ascribed to the Brassicaceae crop's allelopathic chemicals, the lack of nutrient limits, and conventional management practices. However, crop yield was positively related to total soil nitrogen and microbial activity.

1. Broccoli plantation in Mediterranean South region (Spain).

KEYWORDS

Biofertilizers, conventional fertilization, broccoli soil nutrients, plant growth; microbial activity, abundance activity.

AUTHORSHIP

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